

N E R C

Data Holdings

C a t a l o g u e

July 1998

NERC's environmental data

A key resource

As the lead body in the UK for research, survey, monitoring and training in the environmental sciences, the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) has two key resources: its expert work force and its scientific data holdings. Data are the lifeblood of scientific research, and NERC plays a key rôle in environmental data management, with an international reputation in the field.

Almost all environmental data are unique in the time of sampling, and changing conditions may make recollection impossible. Many of NERC's data sets are therefore irreplaceable. Series of measurements accumulated over decades, and historical records dating back to the 19th century are crucial evidence about our environment today; tracing its past development helps to predict future changes. It was through records collected over thirty years that NERC scientists first identified the hole in the ozone layer. NERC's data archives will doubtless hold the key to new environmental questions as yet unasked.

Environmental data relate to such a wide variety of scientific disciplines that responsibility for them is best distributed amongst specialists with appropriate expertise. The responsibility for NERC's data has therefore been divided on discipline-related lines between specialist Data Centres (see far right) liaising closely together so that NERC's data resource is managed as a coherent whole. Full details of the Data Centres are given at the back of this document.

NERC's data policy

NERC's data policy can be found on the world wide web and is available as a booklet. It has been formulated to be consistent both with legal frameworks such as the Environmental Information Regulations and contractual arrangements with other bodies whereby, for example, NERC holds their data on a confidential basis without owning the intellectual property rights.

NERC aims to realise the value of its data resource by using it to further scientific understanding, create wealth and improve the quality of life. This can be done in a variety of ways including: using data sets within NERC's own institutes; giving, exchanging or licensing/selling them to other scientific researchers; or licensing/selling them to commercial organisations which will themselves create wealth. Data are thus a potentially tradeable asset.

Teams and individuals who have collected data sets are allowed a reasonable period of exclusive use during which to analyse them and publish results.

Charges for data are dependent on the uses to which the data will be put, with any consequent restrictions being specified in formal licence agreements. Revenue from commercial applications of NERC's data contributes towards the substantial costs of collection and long term data management. By contrast, NERC wishes to ensure inexpensive access to its holdings by bona fide academic researchers; ie those whose research is solely to advance knowledge and not for commercial gain, and who will publish their results in the open literature. According to circumstances, data are supplied to such users either wholly free of charge, for a nominal handling fee, or at an appropriately discounted rate.

NERC Data Centres

The NERC Designated Data Centres have overall responsibility for all NERC data, the divisions between them being based on scientific discipline or geography as follows:

Accessing and using NERC data

An overview of the Data Centres and their holdings is given in the main sections of this catalogue and on the world wide web. Some NERC data are routinely published in summary form, eg in the annual Hydrological Data UK Yearbooks from the National Water Archive. Digital data in the form of standard products/packages are now usually supplied on CD ROM. Data supplied in response to specific requests are made available on a variety of modern computer compatible media. An increasing number of NERC data sets are being made available on-line via the world wide web.

A range of software tools is required to process such a diversity of data. NERC scientists themselves employ a variety of proprietary software products, both specialist and general purpose - eg geographical information systems. NERC itself supplies software packages for storage, manipulation and analysis of environmental data in specialist application areas. Such packages can be used with data from both NERC and other sources.

Further information, generally including more detailed catalogues, can be obtained from the Data Centres' home pages on the world wide web. These are accessible from NERC's home page URL <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/>

Some of the Data Centres also supply more sophisticated catalogue products, typically for use on personal computers, to help enquirers locate the data they need. Some of NERC's substantial data products are supplied as packages which come complete with the software necessary to search and browse them.

Enquiries or requests for specific data sets should be sent directly to the Data Centres via e-mail, telephone, fax or mail.

Oceanographic data

British Oceanographic Data Centre

BODC

Atmospheric data

British Atmospheric Data Centre

BADC

Earth sciences data

National Geosciences Information Service*

NGIS

Hydrological data

National Water Archive

NWA

Terrestrial/freshwater ecological data

Environmental Information Centre

EIC

NERC data collected in the Antarctic

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre

AEDC

Remotely sensed imagery from satellites and aircraft

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

NEODC

*NERC's Science Based Archaeology community is encouraged to deposit its data with the Archaeology Data Service, Dept of Archaeology, University of York, Kings Manor, York YO1 2EP. Tel: 01904 433954, fax: 01904 433939, e-mail: info@ads.ahds.ac.uk, web site: <http://ads.ahds.ac.uk/>

BRITISH OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA CENTRE (BODC)

BODC is hosted by NERC's Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences at the CCMS Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory on the Wirral. In addition to its role as NERC's Designated Data Centre for marine data, BODC is part of an international network of national oceanographic data centres collaborating under the auspices of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO. It has an international reputation for managing data from large scale, multi-disciplinary oceanographic field experiments and for developing innovative marine data products. BODC is responsible for maintaining the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) on behalf of the IOC and the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO).

DIGITAL DATA PRODUCTS PUBLISHED BY BODC

The GEBCO Digital Atlas **CD ROM**

This digital atlas represents the first seamless, high quality, digital bathymetric contour chart of the world's oceans. Published in vector form, it is accompanied by a high resolution world coastline and a geographically referenced set of undersea feature names. It is supplied with an IBM-compatible PC software package which allows the atlas contents to be viewed interactively and for selected extracts to be exported into the user's own applications. A coloured brochure is available on request.

BOFS North Atlantic Project **CD ROM**

The Biogeochemical Ocean Flux Study (BOFS) was a NERC Community Research Project to study the role of the oceans in the global cycling of carbon. The field programme comprised 11 deep sea cruises between May 1989 and July 1991 and involved over 100 scientists and technicians from 11 universities and 4 NERC laboratories. In addition to physical oceanographic data, a wide range of biological and chemical measurements was also collected from in-situ sensors, water samples, net hauls, sediment traps, and cores. The CD ROM contains the final project data set encompassing 98% of the data collected.

NERC North Sea Project Data Set **CD ROM**

The North Sea Project undertook a concerted multidisciplinary study of circulation, transport and production in the southern North Sea. During the main data collection period (August 1988 - October 1989) survey cruises were repeated monthly following the same 1800 nautical mile track. These were interspersed with process study cruises investigating some particular aspect of the dynamics of the North Sea. Follow-up cruises were undertaken during the next 12 months. The CD ROM contains the final project dataset covering 98% of the data collected over the 38 cruises of the field programme.

OMEX-I Project Data Set **CD ROM**

The Ocean Margin Exchange Project, OMEX-I, was a large-scale, multinational project within the European Union's Marine Science and Technology programme. Its aim was to study the physical, chemical and biological processes at the ocean margin of the Northwest European continental shelf. The project's field programme, from April 1993 to December 1995, involved 200 scientists from 35 institutes and comprised 47 cruises on research vessels from nine European countries. Data were collected not only in the water column but also in the atmospheric and benthic boundary layers. BODC acted as the OMEX-I Project Data Centre and assembled 95% of the 600 data sets collected. These data have been published by BODC as a double CD-ROM.

UKDMAP: The UK Digital Marine Atlas **CD ROM**

UKDMAP is a unique reference work on the seas around the British Isles which is of interest to schools, research workers, planners and engineers alike. It covers a variety of themes, including: general reference; marine geology and geomorphology; marine and coastal parks; reserves and protected areas; marine and coastal conservation in Great Britain; sea birds; sea mammals; marine biology; currents; tides and surges; winds; waves and weather; sea water temperature; chemical distributions; exploitation of the marine environment; fishing areas; fish spawning areas; and BODC data catalogues.

While not a full geographic information system, the atlas is a versatile tool. Users can select and display any of 500 coloured charts, with facilities including zoom, overlay, viewing associated text, querying on specific locations and output of associated graphical or textual information. It runs in Windows 95. A coloured brochure is available on request.

GLOSS Station Handbook: **Global Sea Level Observing System CD ROM**

This is a comprehensive database of information about the 308 tide gauge stations that currently make up the IOC's GLOSS network. In addition there is a complete listing of the 42 500 station years of monthly mean sea level data held by the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level as of June 1996 and covering 1750 stations worldwide. The package includes a simple user interface and viewable copies of the IOC's manuals on sea level measurement and interpretation.

European Directory of Marine Environmental Data (EDMED) **World Wide Web**

With funding from the EU Marine Science and Technology Programme, BODC has been responsible for designing and compiling an extensive directory of the marine environmental datasets held within the Member States of

the EU. The directory contains descriptions of over 2000 data sets from almost 500 laboratories in Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, Poland, Portugal and the UK. It is directly accessible over the world wide web ([URL=http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/edmed.html](http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/edmed.html)) with an inbuilt search engine for selecting data set descriptions by geographic area, data type or source laboratory.

BODC DATA HOLDINGS

BODC holds an extensive range of data sets which can be made available to users. These range from national holdings of tide gauge data, CTD data, instrumentally collected wave data, moored current meter data and met/ocean data from buoys, weatherships and oil rigs to project orientated datasets of physical, biological and chemical data.

Detailed descriptions of these data sets may be found via the world wide web through BODC's Home Page. Examples of major data sets assembled and maintained by BODC include:

- North Sea Project Data Set (1988-90)
- BOFS North Atlantic Data Set (1989-91)
- BOFS Southern Oceans Data Set (1992)
- PRIME Arabesque Indian Ocean Data Set (1994)
- PRIME Mesocosm Experiment & North Atlantic Cruise Data Set (1995-96)
- Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS) marine data set (1992-)
- World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) Sea Level Data Set
- UK contribution to the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) (1991-)
- Ocean Margin Exchange (OMEX) Project Data Set (1993-)
- Joint Air-Sea Interaction (JASIN) Project Data Set (1978)
- Mediterranean-Alpine Experiment (MEDALPEX) Sea Level Data Set (1981-82)
- UK Cruise Summary Reports (1970-)
- UK National Databank of Coastal Tide Gauge Data (1842-)
- UK National Databank of Moored Current Meter Data (1967-)
- UK National Databank of CTD/STD profiles (1975-)
- UK classical hydrographic station data set (1893-)
- UK National Databank of Wave Data (Short term statistics) (1955-)
- One-dimensional Wave Spectra collected by UK Laboratories (1976-)

- UK Offshore Operators Association (UKOOA) Met/Ocean Data Set (1973-88)
- Sea Rover/SeaSoar basin scale traverses of the North Atlantic (1981-91)
- POL Databank of Bottom Pressure Recorder Data (1970-83)
- NW European Shelf/Tidal Current Constituent Data Bank (1970-88)
- North Sea Wave Model (NORSWAM) Input Data Set (1966-76)
- Bristol Channel Suspended Sediments Data Bank (1974-78)
- North Atlantic Ocean Weather Ship (OWS) Hydrocast Data (1910-90)

CURRENT BODC ACTIVITIES

- Project Data Centre for:
 - a. Marine component of NERC's Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS)
 - b. EU Ocean Margin Exchange (OMEX) project
 - c. UK component of the Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS)
 - d. NERC Plankton Reactivity in the Marine Environment (PRIME) project
 - e. UK component of World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE)
 - f. EU Inlet Dynamics Initiative - Algarve (INDIA) project
 - g. EU Processes of Vertical Exchange in Shelf Seas (PROVESS) project.
- WOCE Data Assembly Centre for Sea Level Data
- Data Centre for the UK National Tide Gauge Network
- UK Digital Marine Atlas Project
- IOC/IHO General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans
- EU European Directory of Marine Environmental Data

BODC CONTACTS

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Home page: <http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/bodcmain.html>

COMPLEMENTARY ACTIVITIES TO BODC

Commencing in the second half of 1998, NERC has funded a three year programme to establish an archive of NERC's deep ocean geophysics data at the Southampton Oceanography Centre.

Details can be found on the world wide web at <http://www.soc.soton.ac.uk/CHD/SeaDOG/>

NERC also funds the British Ocean Sediment Core Repository (BOSCOR) at Southampton Oceanography Centre where more than 400 cores are held.

Further information about BOSCOR can be found on the world wide web at:

<http://www.soc.soton.ac.uk/CHD/BOSCOR/>

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC)

The British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) is the Natural Environment Research Council's (NERC) Designated Data Centre for the Atmospheric Sciences. It is sited at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in Oxfordshire, part of the Central Laboratory of the Research Councils (CLRC). The BADC has substantial data holdings and also provides links to information and data held by other data centres.

BADC DATA HOLDINGS

The BADC holds atmospheric data and related data sets. These data are derived from a wide variety of sources including satellite instruments, computer models and ground-based, aircraft and balloon observations.

The data held at the BADC fall naturally into three types:

- Data sets produced by NERC-funded programmes such as ACSOE, HYREX, ISAMS and the MST radar.
- 3rd-party Meteorological data sets, including observational data from the UK Met Office and model data from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) which are required as baseline data by a broad section of the atmospheric research community.
- Other 3rd-party data sets which are required by a broad section of the research community. These include a collection of data on CD ROM which is available on the world wide web for browsing.

DATA FROM NERC PROGRAMMES

The BADC is the designated archive for atmospheric data which are produced as a result of NERC-funded research in the atmospheric sciences. It also provides a number of data support services to NERC research programmes.

For the ACSOE programme (Atmospheric Chemistry Studies in the Oceanic Environment) the BADC has provided the long-term data archive and a simple mechanism to allow experimenters to deposit files at the BADC to allow sharing of results during the campaign. In addition to measurements of atmospheric chemistry made during the campaigns, the archive contains other subsidiary data such as 5-day back trajectories which were produced to help experimenters to plan and interpret their measurements.

The BADC also holds data from a number of other NERC-funded programmes including rainfall data from the Hydrological Radar Experiment (HYREX), data from the MST radar at Capel Dewi near Aberystwyth and the ISAMS instrument on the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite.

Over the next few years, BADC will be acquiring data sets from new NERC programmes in the atmospheric sciences such as the UTLS/OZONE project and the atmospheric data from the URGENT programme.

THE NERC - UKMO DATA AGREEMENT

Under the terms of an agreement between NERC and the UK Met. Office, requests for meteorological data from NERC-funded researchers are coordinated by the BADC. This arrangement is designed to increase efficiency, reduce costs to NERC and avoid duplicate requests. Certain data sets for which there is a high demand have been acquired in bulk and made available through the BADC. Current examples of these include observational data sets from the Met. Office and ECMWF model data sets which are described in more detail in the next sections.

BADC MET OFFICE OBSERVATIONAL DATA

The BADC holds three main observational data sets from the Met Office archives - climate station data, synoptic station data and radiosonde data. The climate station data consist of daily measurements of a large number of atmospheric parameters from approx 900 surface stations across the UK for the period 1959-present. The synoptic station data set contains measurements of similar parameters from 218 UK and European stations at hourly intervals for the period 1990-present. Radiosonde data are held for 160 European stations and consist of vertical profiles of temperature, wind and humidity at 6-hourly intervals.

BADC METEOROLOGICAL MODEL DATA

Under the NERC-UKMO Data Agreement the BADC has acquired extensive meteorological analyses from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF). These include high resolution spectral and gridded temperature and wind data from the ECMWF Re-Analysis (ERA) project in which model analyses were generated for the period 1979-1994 using the same version of the model, thus producing a coherent time-series of considerable value for climate studies. More recent data from the operational analyses are also acquired and updated regularly. The data include 2.5 degree gridded temperatures, winds, humidity and a range of surface parameters. Using wind data from ECMWF, series of 5-day back trajectories from a dense grid of points over the UK and Atlantic are also made available.

OTHER BADC DATA SETS

The BADC holds a number of other 3rd party data sets such as data from the chemistry instruments HALOE, CLAES, MLS and ISAMS on the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite, stratospheric analyses from the Met

Office, global ozone measurements from the NASA Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer (TOMS). These data sets are updated daily with current data. A CD ROM jukebox holds 3rd-party data sets on over 30 CD ROMs.

ACCESS TO BADC DATA HOLDINGS

All BADC data sets are held on-line. Extensive information on the BADC data sets is available through the BADC world wide web. The BADC web address is <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>. In many cases this is also the route to the data themselves. However, some have restrictions on their access. For example, all users of meteorological data sets supplied through the UK Meteorological Office must sign a Data Protocol before gaining access to the data. For this reason, not all of the BADC data sets are available through the world wide web. In these cases, users are provided with an account on the BADC computer once they have signed the Protocol and the data are then accessed via ftp.

BADC data sets are catalogued. The catalogue can be searched by keyword or categories eg meteorology, climate, dynamics, chemistry etc.

Software is provided to assist in the manipulation of the data and extensive information is provided on the data collection procedures, formats, data quality, contact names and references to journal papers. Other specialist services include the development of value-added data products such as averaged and gridded data and the generation of video sequencing of data for viewing large data sets over long periods. For example, a video tape of the entire sequence of TOMS total ozone maps is available.

BADC World Wide Web Links

The BADC world wide web service also provides an excellent collection of links to sites running world wide web servers offering data and information relevant to the atmospheric sciences (<http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>). The collection of links can be searched by keyword or browsed by category. There are also links to web search facilities and public domain software archives.

CURRENT BADC DATA SETS

Major data sets held by the BADC include those in the following list. The world wide web catalogue entry indicates any access restrictions, whether the dataset is available on line, and on what other media, if any, it can be supplied. A full description is provided as illustrated below.

AAOE: Airborne Antarctic Ozone Experiment
AASE: Airborne Arctic Stratospheric Expedition
AASE II: Airborne Arctic Stratospheric Expedition II
Aberporth High Resolution Radiosonde Data
ACSOE: Atmospheric Chemistry Studies in the Ocean Environment
ASHOE: Airborne Southern Hemisphere Ozone Experiment
CIRA: Cospar International Reference Atmosphere
CLAES: Cryogenic Limb Array Etalon Spectrometer
CLIM: Climate Station Data
EAAM: Effective Atmosphere Angular Momentum
EASOE: European Arctic Stratosphere Ozone Experiment
ECMWF Operational Analyses
ECMWF Trajectories
ECMWF Gridded data
ERA: ECMWF Re-Analysis project
GEDEX: Greenhouse Effect Detection Experiment
GOSTA: Global Ocean Surface Temperature Atlas
HALOE: Halogen Occultation Experiment
HYREX: Hydrological Radar Experiment
ISAMS: Improved Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder
LIMS: Limb Infra-Red Monitor of the Stratosphere
MLS: Microwave Limb Sounder
MST: Mesosphere Stratosphere Troposphere Radar
RAD: Radiosonde Data
SAM II: Stratospheric Aerosol Measurement II
SAMS: Stratosphere and Mesosphere Sounder
SPADE: Stratosphere Photochemistry, Aerosols and Dynamics Expedition
SRB: Surface Radiation Budget
STEP: Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange Project
SYNOP: Synoptic Station Data
TOMS: Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer
TOVS UKMO Analyses: Tiros Operational Vertical Sounder Analyses
UKMO UARS Assimilated Data

BADC CONTACTS

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E-mail: badc@rl.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>

List of all datasets held at the BADC

Online CD-ROM VHS Video

Not Available Anonymously; BADC Account Required

● AAOE: Airborne Antarctic Ozone Experiment

Measurements from a NASA aircraft campaign to study chemical composition and physical parameters in the Antarctic during the development of the Antarctic Ozone Hole in August and September 1987. The data include atmospheric composition from a variety of instruments, meteorological parameters, aerosol and cloud data.

NATIONAL GEOSCIENCES INFORMATION SERVICE (NGIS)

The National Geosciences Information Service (NGIS) is operated by the British Geological Survey and is the focus and repository for the majority of the nation's geosciences data and information. It represents the public interface to the Survey's data resources and expertise, and it is responsible for the provision of advice on geological matters and for the dissemination of data in forms meaningful and relevant to end users.

STANDARD NGIS DIGITAL DATA PRODUCTS

British Borehole Catalogue **CD ROM**

This catalogue provides an index to over 550 000 boreholes and wells across Britain held in the Survey's National Geological Records Centre. The index can be searched by OS map background or gazetteer and provides details of the position, depth, reference and status of each borehole. It is published in conjunction with Geoinformation International and incorporates ArcView Publisher viewing software to run on a Windows based PC.

Interactive Geoscience Atlas: The Lake District and Adjacent areas **CD ROM**

This multimedia application is based on digital geochemical and geological maps from the Lake District geochemical atlas. These are linked, via icons and a menu system to geophysical and Landsat images. In addition enhanced digital pictures of scenery, geological features, mines, quarries, fossils, mineral specimens, rock thin sections and paleo-environment models are included. Versions are available to run on PC DOS/Windows or Apple Macintosh systems.

Physical Properties of the Major Aquifers of England and Wales **CD ROM**

Summarised data on aquifer physical properties; Transmissivity, Storage Coefficient, Porosity and Permeability, have been collated on a CD ROM with a simple map based user interface designed for use on Windows 95/NT machines. The data is also accessible from Windows 3.x systems with an alternative map browser, and from PC-DOS without maps. The CD ROM is available as an annex to a printed report on the aquifer properties compiled in collaboration with the Environment Agency.

Tectonic Map of Britain, Ireland and adjacent areas

This dataset has been generated from a database of separate files, compiled at a 1:1 000 000 scale, comprising pre-Quaternary solid geology, tectonic linework, ornaments and text labels. The tectonic linework file is structured so that the different ages and categories of structure can be readily extracted. It can be provided in a range of vector formats for loading into a user's GIS. The map has been compiled as a collaborative venture with the Geological Survey of Ireland and has also been released in simplified form as a lithoprinted edition.

Geological Maps of United Kingdom

Digital versions of the 1:625 000-scale solid and Quaternary geology maps and the 1:250 000-scale solid geology map series (onshore geology) can be supplied as complete datasets in a range of raster or vector formats. The solid geology and drift mapping at 1:50 000-scale is being progressively released in digital form. These data sets can be directly loaded into a user's GIS, or can be used to produce customised maps.

Address Linked Geological Inventory (ALGI)

This system has been developed to enable the rapid production of computer-generated geological reports providing site-specific information about ground conditions at Post Code level. Present coverage comprises Bristol and the London area.

GeoMedia Services

Through a business agreement with Intergraph (UK) Ltd access to the BGS Borehole Index is now available over the Internet. This service allows selected records to be purchased using Secure Electronic Transaction (SET).

NGIS DATA HOLDINGS

Since 1835 BGS has been involved in the creation of a National Archive of geological information for strategic and research purposes. Statutory regulations have ensured the deposition of large quantities of sub-surface information as of right. Exchange agreements have also added much reference material, especially from overseas. Today these collections represent one of the world's largest databases of geoscientific materials.

Datasets for the following areas are available:

United Kingdom	Africa
UK Continental Shelf	South America
Northwest Europe	Southeast Asia
Northwest European Shelf	

The data relate to:

geology: general; boreholes; maps; reports; samples;
biostratigraphy; marine: sedimentology
geophysics: general; boreholes; maps; samples;
geomagnetism; geothermal; marine; remote-sensing;
seismology (earthquakes and profiles)
geochemistry: general; maps; minerals; analytical; mineralogy;
petrology
geotechnics: general; maps; reports; engineering geology;
hydrogeology; mining
geography
bibliography

Further details are given on the world wide web

The British Geological Survey Lexicon of Named Rock Units

© British Geological Survey

To use this dictionary, please enter the name or part-name of the rock unit that interests you, then click the "Submit Query" button. Alternatively, you can search by Computer Code or Preferred Map Code, if these are known. Searches may also be specified and performed on the basis of the Maximum Age of the rock unit or the Status Code.

Searches can be carried out using one or any combination of these criteria.

For an explanation of the status codes used in this database, please click [here](#).

WARNING: Database queries can take up to 5 minutes to execute, depending upon the level of system use.

Rock Unit: Computer Code:

Preferred Map Code: Status Code:

Maximum Age of Rock Unit:

For further information or comments on the Lexicon of Named Rock Units, please contact td.fletcher@bgs.ac.uk

The BGS Lexicon of Named Rock Units

The Lexicon of Named Rock Units is a powerful relational database holding definitive and readily accessible information about rock units used on BGS maps and in BGS publications. Although built as a reference for BGS geoscientists, it provides a useful first stop for those interested in stratigraphy and rock terminology in the UK.

BGS Research Reports

In cooperation with the Geological Society, the BGS Stratigraphy Committee has reviewed the stratigraphical classification and nomenclature for all parts of Great Britain for which modern information is available. The first reports dealing with the Carboniferous rocks of the Midland Valley of Scotland and the stratigraphical framework for the Ordovician of Snowdonia and the Lleyn Peninsula are available for download.

The Igneous Rock Classification

The BGS has produced a new integrated scheme for rock classification that is suitable for both field and laboratory use. Its hierarchical structure means that classification is appropriate to the level of information available. The scheme dealing with igneous rocks is available for download.

Map Symbols and Ornaments

The BGS has brought together a complete listing of all its geological cartographic symbols in current usage and is making them available in one downloadable document. An additional listing of lithological ornaments used on diagrams in BGS publications is included.

LIBRARY

Access to the Library OPAC listing its holdings, including BGS publications, external publications by staff, and many unpublished open-file reports and maps can be made via Telnet and the world wide web. Alternatively it can be accessed directly via JANET.

CONTACTS

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Home page: <http://www.bgs.ac.uk/>

DIGITAL DATA

A wide range of digital data is available under licence from BGS. Typical digital products include:

Raster-scanned and vectorised, fully attributed geological maps at small scales (1:250 000 and 1:625 000), medium scale (1:50 000) and large scale (1:10 000)

Multi-element analyses of stream sediments, soils, heavy mineral pan concentrates and stream waters from the UK Geochemical baseline programme - GBASE

Multi-element analyses of rocks, drill core, soils, heavy minerals and stream sediments from the UK 'Minerals Programme'

World Mineral Statistical Database (detailing world-wide production, consumption and trade in minerals)

Directory of Mines and Quarries and related GIS products (MINGOL)

Multi-element analyses of sea-bed sediments for the UK continental shelf

Locations of BGS boreholes and shallow samples for UK continental shelf

BGS marine gravity data for the UK continental shelf

BGS gravity data for onshore UK

BGS aeromagnetic data covering the entire UK land area and most of the Atlantic Margin

Aeromagnetic data for the North Sea

Data at one-minute resolution from three UK magnetic observatories available next day

Hydrogeological data, including lithologies, borehole construction, water levels, aquifer properties and chemical analyses of groundwaters from the UK National Groundwater Survey and associated programmes

INTERNET PUBLISHING

BGS now provides an increasing number of free publications and other products through its web site. Details are given in the Free Products page. Examples are listed in the next column.

NATIONAL WATER ARCHIVE (NWA)

The National Water Archive (NWA) is maintained by the Institute of Hydrology at Wallingford, Oxfordshire, a component institute of NERC's Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. A broad range of hydrological - and related - data are being assimilated into the coordinated management provided by the NWA. Data holdings range from the catchment scale, eg detailed climatological and hydrological data for a network of experimental catchments, to national river flow data and DTM and international coverage (world's flood archive).

PUBLICATIONS: THE HYDROLOGICAL DATA UK SERIES

The Hydrological Data UK series of publications is a series of Yearbooks and reports relating to nationally archived hydrological data. The objective of the series is to furnish the data necessary to document year-on-year variations in hydrological conditions and water resources and provide authoritative interpretation of significant trends and hydrological events. Component publications include:

Yearbooks

The Yearbooks moved from hard copy form to world wide web pages for the 1996 edition. Both varieties bring together the principal data sets relating to river flow, groundwater levels and areal rainfall for the United Kingdom. A comprehensive hydrological review of the year is included together with, where appropriate, feature articles describing noteworthy events or hydrometric developments. Whereas the publication date for the hard copy was in the succeeding December, the electronic version is posted as the data become available.

Hydrometric Register and Statistics volumes

These companion publications to the Yearbooks are published in a 5-year cycle. They provide detailed statistical information relating to the featured 5-year period and are a reference source for hydrometric data which does not change materially from year to year. The latest edition, covering the period 1991-95, contains maps, tables and statistics for over 1000 river basins and 150 representative boreholes throughout the UK. Two earlier editions have been published for 1981-85 and 1986-90 and are still available but in short supply.

Hydrological Monitoring

The Institute of Hydrology and British Geological Survey jointly operate a national hydrological monitoring programme on behalf of Government and the Environment Agencies of Great Britain. Hydrological data are routinely supplied by a number of regional and national authorities concerned with the measurement of hydrometric variables. Data held on the National River Flow Archive and National Groundwater Level Archive provide the necessary historical perspective within which the severity of drought or flood episodes can be assessed. As part of the monitoring programme, reports on

rainfall, river flows, groundwater levels and reservoir contents are published monthly (by the tenth working day). These Hydrological Summaries for Great Britain - typically 14 pages in length - form the basis of a range of briefing notes, articles and technical papers aimed at increasing scientific and public awareness of hydrological and water resources issues.

Reports on notable hydrological events

Occasional reports in the Hydrological Data UK series are prepared to mark outstanding hydrological events. The latest of these examines the 1988-92 drought in a water resources framework and establishes an important benchmark against which future periods of protracted rainfall deficiency may be compared.

NWA DATA HOLDINGS

The principal data sets fall into two general categories: time series and spatial. Examples of major data holdings appear below.

Time Series

National River Flow Archive
National Groundwater Level Archive
Flood Event Archive
Monthly Catchment Areal Rainfall
FRIEND European Flow Database
World Floods Data set
Experimental catchment and automatic weather station data
Soil moisture content databank
Annual maxima and Flood Peaks-over-a-threshold archives

Spatial Data Sets

Continuous and fully structured digitised rivers at 1:50 000
Hydrological Digital Terrain Model (IHDTM) of the UK
(1km grid)
Hydrology of Soil Types map (HOST) (1km grid)
Digital representation of average rainfall and evaporation
(1km grid)
Flood Studies report maps
FRIEND European climate and catchment characteristics
100 year flood risk map of England and Wales
Vector catchment boundaries

Access arrangements vary between data sets.

The National River Flow Archive (NRFA)

The exploitation and management of water resources and river systems depends to a considerable degree on the ready availability of hydrological data. To service a very broadly-based need for river flow data the UK maintains a network of over 1200 gauging stations. The relatively dense network is a necessary response to the heterogeneity of the UK in terms of its climate, geology, land use and patterns of water utilisation.

Some gauging stations are maintained by the Institute of Hydrology in their experimental catchments but most flow measurement is undertaken by the Environment Agency in England and Wales and by the Scottish Environment Protection Agency in Scotland; the Departments of Agriculture and Environment undertake a joint operation in Northern Ireland.

The NRFA currently holds over 30 000 station years of daily and monthly river flow data together with monthly peak flows and catchment rainfall totals. For a few strategically important catchments naturalised flows (ie adjusted to take account of the net effect of upstream abstractions and discharges) are also archived.

NRFA data are published in the Hydrological Data UK series of Yearbooks and reports, and made available through a comprehensive retrieval service with a wide selection of standard retrieval options, which include:

- Tables of daily mean flows (gauged or naturalised)
- Hydrographs of daily or monthly mean flows
- Tables of monthly extreme flows
- Flow duration statistics
- Catchment monthly rainfall and runoff totals
- Running mean plots of annual maximum or minimum flows for selected gauging stations

Further details are given on the world wide web and in the Hydrological Data UK series of publications. Potential users are invited to contact the NWA to discuss the facilities available and their particular needs.

LOIS Rivers Data Centre

This is based at Wallingford and is responsible for the assembly of chemical flux data from the Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS) thematic programme and the Environment Agency (EA). It includes data relating to: water quality, water quantity, consent to discharge, abstraction licences and biology. Additionally, spatial data sets of land form, land cover, infrastructure and soils are held. Data dissemination is through a series of CD ROMs. The URL for the LOIS home page is: <http://www.npm.ac.uk/pml/loisa.html>

NWA CONTACTS

Requests for any NWA data, and enquiries about the NWA retrieval service should be directed to:

The National Water Archive Office
 CEH Institute of Hydrology
 Wallingford
 Oxfordshire
 OX10 8BB

Tel: +44 (0) 1491 692468
 Fax: +44 (0) 1491 692424
 E-mail: nwamail@oh.ac.uk
 Home page: <http://www.nwl.ac.uk>

A guide to the variation in overall reservoir stocks in England and Wales

An illustration of overall reservoir stocks for England and Wales for recent years

ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION CENTRE (EIC)

EIC is hosted by the Institute of Terrestrial Ecology at Monks Wood in Cambridgeshire, a component institute of NERC's Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. The EIC sits at the hub of a distributed data network of regional centres and data managers throughout each of the six ITE research stations. In addition to its role as NERC's Designated Data Centre responsible for terrestrial and freshwater ecological data, EIC takes a leading part in many data-centred programmes of cross-disciplinary research for both European and UK government agencies and commercial companies. It has strong links with UK and European universities, carrying out collaborative research programmes, and providing student placements at both undergraduate and post-graduate levels.

STANDARD EIC PRODUCTS AVAILABLE ON DISKETTE

CIS: Countryside Information System

The CIS is a Microsoft Windows-based software program developed to give policy advisors, planners, researchers, students and teachers easy access to information about the British countryside. Commissioned by the UK's Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions, the CIS includes a wide range of environmental data - including landscape features, vegetation, habitats and topography - for each square on a one kilometre grid of Great Britain. Further information about CIS can be obtained from the world wide web.

CIS: Environmental Catalogue

The CIS Environmental Catalogue is a Microsoft Windows-based hypertext database that provides all the necessary information required to allow users of the CIS to identify and obtain data sets available in CIS format. The catalogue describes all the data sets available, and provides information on the original surveys and definitions, and details of the data suppliers.

EIC DATA HOLDINGS

The Centre maintains an extensive range of data sets which can be made available to enquirers. An index of data sets is available and can be accessed via the world wide web. The following list provides information on some of the major data holdings:

Database of the Biological Records Centre

The Biological Records Centre (BRC), a component of EIC, is the UK's national biodiversity data centre. The BRC database comprises about six million records of the distributions of over 15 000 biological species in the British Isles. The majority of the data is donated by volunteer recorders and is received through national recording schemes managed by the BRC. The database is used to publish distribution atlases and to provide computerised retrieval and mapping services.

CORINE Biotopes Inventory

The database is a computerised inventory of sites of international importance for nature conservation in 13 member states of the European Union (EU). It is currently being extended to other countries in central and eastern Europe. Records identify the location and extent of over 7000 sites, with descriptions of important habitats and biological species, rationale for notification and protection status. The inventory forms a layer of the European Union CORINE GIS on the state of the environment of the EU, co-ordinated by the European Environment Agency (EEA).

Database of Critical Loads of Atmospheric Pollutants

The database comprises estimates of the sensitivity of the land surface of Great Britain to the effects of atmospheric pollution (particularly acid deposition), on the basis of air quality and the sensitivity of receptor soils, geology, freshwaters and vegetation (trees, semi-natural vegetation and crops). The database is managed by the Critical Loads Mapping and Data Centre (MADC) at the EIC and acts as the UK National Focal Centre for the Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions, to develop national critical loads and levels maps.

Ecological Surveys of Great Britain (Countryside Survey)

The database includes information collected in field surveys of selected 1 km squares of the British National Grid, representative of 32 distinct Land Classes (classified according to environmental characteristics such as geology, altitude and climate derived from maps). Information includes botanical data (occurrence and cover within experimental quadrats), soil type and strata, and land cover, and the data have been collected from up to 508 sample squares, surveyed in 1978, 1984, 1990 and 1998. The data are regarded as being representative of the land classes and, by classifying every 1 km square of the National Grid, it is possible to make statistical predictions of probable ecological characteristics.

The Land Cover Map of Great Britain

The Land Cover Map is a digital map derived from the classification of cloud-free satellite images from the American Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM). Produced by ITE's Earth Observation Section the map identifies 25 land cover types, which include built up areas, arable farm land, pastures and forestry, together with a variety of semi-natural vegetation types. The classes are mapped on a 25 metre raster overlay on the British National Grid to cover the complete land surface of Great Britain.

Database of the NERC United Kingdom Environmental Change Network

The Environmental Change Network (ECN) is a multi-agency, long-term monitoring programme for identifying and

quantifying environmental changes associated with man's activities. Hosted by ITE's research station at Merlewood in Cumbria, measurements are collected regularly at a growing number of network sites (currently 10 terrestrial and 37 freshwater) throughout the UK, using standardized protocols. The data cover a wide range of physical, chemical and biological parameters including climate, air quality, water quality and flow, soil development and chemistry, invertebrates, vertebrates, vegetation, land use and site management practice. Further information about ECN data can be obtained from the world wide web at <http://www.nmw.ac.uk/ecn/index.html>

Analytical Chemistry Databases

The databases are maintained by the Analytical Sections of ITE research stations at Monks Wood and Merlewood, and include the results of over 300 000 biological samples that have been analysed for over 2 million individual determinands. The majority of the Merlewood data relates to water, soil and vegetation analyses for major and minor nutrient and trace elements and the major ions. The Monks Wood data relate to pesticide and toxic chemical residues in both vertebrate and invertebrate tissue, soils, water and vegetation.

CURRENT EIC PROJECTS

Major programmes and projects with which EIC is involved:

CEO	Centre for Earth Observation
CIS	Countryside Information System
CS2000	Countryside Survey 2000
ECN	The NERC Environmental Change Network
ED	The NERC Environmental Diagnostics Programme
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network
FP4	The European Fourth Framework Programme
LINK	British National Space Centre Earth Observation LINK programme
LOIS	The NERC Land Ocean Interaction Study
TIGER	The NERC Terrestrial Initiative in Global Environmental Research
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme

EIC CONTACTS

Database Manager
 Environmental Information Centre
 CEH Institute of Terrestrial Ecology
 Monks Wood
 Abbots Ripton
 Huntingdon, Cambs. PE17 2LS
 United Kingdom

Tel: +44 (0) 1487 773381
 Fax: +44 (0) 1487 773467
 E-mail: eric@ite.ac.uk
 Home page: <http://www.nmw.ac.uk/ite/eic1.html>

ANTARCTIC ENVIRONMENTAL DATA CENTRE (AEDC)

The Antarctic Environmental Data Centre (AEDC) is the NERC Designated Data Centre for Antarctic data and is located within the British Antarctic Survey (BAS). The AEDC is a 'virtual' data centre providing a gateway to the distributed data holdings of the British Antarctic Survey. It is responsible for ensuring the secure, long term management of BAS data holdings which are individually managed by Principal Investigators and Programme Data Managers.

STANDARD BAS DATA PRODUCTS

The majority of data held by BAS are to support its science programmes. However, a number of standard data products and data resources are available. These include:

Maps of the Antarctic and Antarctica

The BAS Mapping and Geographic Information Centre (MAGIC) produces a range of maps of the Antarctic, including:

- Topographic and Satellite Image Maps (1: 500 000 and 1: 250 000 scale)
- Topographic Maps (1: 200 000 scale)
- Large scale Topographic Maps (Various scales)
- Geoscience Maps (1: 500 000 and various other scales)
- BAS GEOMAP series (Various scales)
- South Georgia Maps (Various Scales)

The BAS on-line map catalogue on the world wide web gives further information.

Antarctic Digital Database

The Antarctic Digital Database (ADD) is the product of an international collaborative project, co-ordinated in the UK by BAS, (through its Mapping and Geographic Information Centre), Scott Polar Research Institute and World Conservation Monitoring Centre under the auspices of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research and its Working Group on Geodesy and Geographic Information. It represents a major development in Antarctic mapping, providing access to the first seamless digital map of Antarctica, with the most up-to-date and complete coastline of the continent now available in digital form. The database has been prepared from cartographic material published by 11 nations, updated with reference to satellite imagery. The ADD provides the common framework to which multidisciplinary data sets can be referred for GIS applications, facilitating retrieval and evaluation of all data, particularly for monitoring environmental changes in Antarctica. The ADD will evolve to meet the geographical data needs of the international Antarctic scientific community and of programme managers.

Meteorological Data

Historical and current meteorological data are available from BAS, and other, stations. They include monthly mean temperature, pressure, total cloud amount and wind speed (knots) data for Faraday (from 1944 to 1995), Halley (from 1956), Rothera (from 1946) and Signy (from 1947). There are

also monthly averages of daily max/min temperatures available for Halley and Rothera. Current station data from the Global Telecommunications System, decoded, are available for all Antarctic stations. These are available about two days behind real time in order to pick up late reports. The latest report from each station (decoded about every hour) is available for ships and for land stations.

Data and Biological Resources Centre

The centre contains a large, and unique, collection of plant, invertebrate and microbial specimens (mainly preserved, but some in culture) from Antarctic and Sub-antarctic regions. In addition to the specimens, the Centre holds physical and chemical data for soils and freshwater, microclimate and bibliographic data. The Resource Centre also houses the British Antarctic Survey herbarium (international code AAS) which contains a large collection of plant specimens (over 38 000) from Antarctica, the sub-Antarctic Islands and surrounding continents (especially Fuegia and Patagonia). Over 2000 taxa are represented, comprising predominantly bryophytes and lichens with smaller collections of vascular plants, macro-algae and macro-fungi. The herbarium includes a large literature collection on the taxonomy and distribution of relevant species and a number of useful bibliographic databases.

BIOMASS

The AEDC holds the master copy of the BIOMASS data set. BIOMASS (Biological Investigations of Marine Antarctic Systems and Stocks) was a major multi-national scientific programme for the study of the Antarctic marine ecosystem and its living resources, with emphasis on krill (*Euphausia superba*). Data were collected between 1980 and 1985 by 34 vessels from 13 countries from a wide area of the Southern Ocean. Data focus on the distribution and population structure of krill, but also include supporting oceanographic and related data.

BAS DATA HOLDINGS

BAS collects data in support of its scientific programmes, covering the geological, biological and physical sciences. The AEDC provides a gateway to these distributed data holdings and should be contacted for further information about the scope and availability of data. An on-line, searchable catalogue of BAS data holdings is accessible from the AEDC web pages. The catalogue includes the facility to produce maps, on-the-fly, to show the location of data collection sites.

The on-line catalogue is produced as part of the BAS Metadata Management System (MDMS) project, which provides Principal Investigators and Data Managers with a facility to enable the systematic recording and management of a standardised set of metadata, or information about data.

INTERNATIONAL LINKAGES

The AEDC is the British National Antarctic Data Centre within the international Antarctic Data Directory System (ADDs). This is an initiative by countries active in Antarctic science to improve access to scientific data from the Antarctic. A key element of the ADDs is the Antarctic Master Directory (AMD), an on-line, searchable catalogue of Antarctic scientific data collected by member countries. The AMD can be accessed via the AEDC web pages. The AEDC played a pivotal role in the establishment of the ADDs and is a major contributor to the international network of Antarctic data managers, defining standards and procedures for the

management of Antarctic metadata and Antarctic data catalogues.

ARCTIC DATA

NERC is funding an Arctic Environmental Metadata Centre (AEMC), located at the Scott Polar Research Institute of the University of Cambridge, to collate information on UK holdings of data relating to the Arctic. This information is available from the AEMC web pages (<http://www.spri.cam.ac.uk/aemc/aemc.htm>). An on-line, searchable catalogue of Arctic datasets is being maintained by the AEDC, within the BAS Metadata Management System, and this can be accessed via the AEMC web pages.

AEDC CONTACTS

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre
British Antarctic Survey
High Cross, Madingley Road
Cambridge CB3 0ET

Tel: +44 (0) 1223 221400
Fax: +44 (0) 1223 362616
E-mail: aedc@bas.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nerc-bas.ac.uk/public/aedc/>

NERC EARTH OBSERVATION DATA CENTRE (NEODC)

The NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC) is based at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL), Didcot, Oxfordshire. It is the Designated Data Centre with responsibility for NERC holdings of Earth observation data.

NERC EARTH OBSERVATION DATA HOLDINGS

NERC holds five main categories of remotely sensed Earth observation data, viz

- NERC satellite data of the Earth's surface, primarily the ATSR Archive held at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
- NERC satellite data of the Earth's atmosphere including for example temperature and chemical constituents please refer to the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) page for further information
- Satellite data of the Earth's atmosphere acquired from international satellites, including present-day and archive data from the NERC Satellite Receiving Station at the University of Dundee, and various NASA and ESA data sets currently available through the BADC
- Satellite data of the Earth's surface acquired from international satellites including AVHRR imagery from the Dundee satellite station, and Landsat, SPOT and ERS imagery, for example, procured from commercial suppliers
- Airborne remotely sensed data of the Earth's surface acquired from NERC's own aircraft

The Rutherford Appleton Laboratory ATSR Archive

The Along-Track Scanning Radiometer (ATSR) archive held at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory constitutes global EO data at a spatial resolution of 1km acquired by the ATSR-1 and ATSR-2 satellite instruments - the former from 1991 and the latter since 1995. The total data archive incorporates rigorously calibrated infra-red imagery for the provision of consistent and accurate observations of global sea-surface temperature and since 1995 three additional calibrated channels in the visible spectrum particularly suited to vegetation monitoring.

For further information contact URL <http://www.atsr.rl.ac.uk/>

The Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Archive

The Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS) has been continuously receiving and archiving data from meteorological satellites (AVHRR and TOVS) since 1976. DSRS holds a complete archive of all raw data back to October 1978. In addition, there are Coastal Zone Colour Scanner (CZCS) data from the NOAA NIMBUS 7 satellite. The digital data are

complemented by browse files of quick-look infra-red and visual images. Quick-look browse file images from all five channels of AVHRR can be viewed on the world wide web.

For further information contact URL
<http://www.sat.dundee.ac.uk/>

The NERC Satellite Image Archive

The NEODC administers a central archive and catalogue of satellite data. The Data Centre holds a modest budget for new acquisitions in support of NERC programmes and is also allocated funding from successful Training and Grant awards which require the purchase of EO data. Such central purchasing aims at avoiding replication of purchase and ensures professional custodianship of valuable data.

The Image Archive contains in excess of 2000 image files mainly derived from the Landsat satellite supplemented by a small Spot archive and an increasing volume of ERS radar imagery. There is total UK coverage of Landsat Thematic Mapper™ and Multispectral Scanner (MSS) scenes. There is also a less extensive archive of foreign scenes, the majority of holdings being in Africa, Europe and Antarctica.

Further information is held on the world wide web at URL
<http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/>

The NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Archive

There is a large archive of NERC airborne campaign data (1982 to present), where the holdings are mainly Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) data and a growing holding of hyperspectral image data from a Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (casi). The archive presently contains more than 8000 image files of multispectral data acquired predominantly in the UK but also in mainland Europe.

NERC also holds an archive of air photography acquired during its airborne remote sensing campaigns.

Web site: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/>

The NERC Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service

The Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service, based at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory, provides processed products from the AVHRR satellite data received at Dundee, for use by environmental scientists who are not specialists in remote sensing, or do not have access to image analysis hardware or software. These include a near real-time service of sea-surface temperature data derived from AVHRR.

Further information is held on the world wide web at URL
<http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsdas/>

NERC EARTH OBSERVATION DATA CENTRE CONTACTS

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

Space Science Department
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton, Didcot
Oxon OX11 0QX

Tel: +44 (0) 1235 446168
Fax: +44 (0) 1235 445848
E-mail: stuart.white@rl.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/>

Dundee Satellite Receiving Station

Dept of Applied Physics, Electronics & Manufacturing
Engineering
University of Dundee
Dundee DD1 4HN

Tel: +44 (0) 1382 344406
Fax: +44 (0) 1382 202575
E-mail: peb@sat.dundee.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.sat.dundee.ac.uk/>

Phytoplankton bloom in the north east Atlantic: this image was created by RSDAS at Plymouth from satellite data received at Dundee, and transmitted to a research vessel sampling in the area.

Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service

CCMS Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Prospect Place
West Hoe
Plymouth PL1 3DH

Tel: +44 (0) 1752 633150
Fax: +44 (0) 1752 666101
E-mail: s.groom@pml.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsdas/>

NEODC holds the archive of multispectral imagery acquired by the NERC remote sensing aircraft.

NERC designated data centres

Further information about NERC's designated data centres can be obtained from its web site: <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/>

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre

British Antarctic Survey
High Cross
Madingley Road
Cambridge
CB3 0ET

Tel: +44 (0) 1223 221400
Fax: +44 (0) 1223 362616
e-mail: aedc@bas.ac.uk
Web site: <http://www.nerc-bas.ac.uk/public/aedc/>

British Atmospheric Data Centre

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton
Didcot
Oxfordshire
OX11 0QX

Tel: +44 (0) 1235 446432
Fax: +44 (0) 1235 445848
e-mail: badc@rl.ac.uk
Web site: <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>

British Oceanographic Data Centre

CCMS Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory
Bidston Observatory
Birkenhead
Merseyside
L43 7RA

Tel: +44 (0) 151 653 8633
Fax: +44 (0) 151 652 3950
e-mail: bodcmail@pol.ac.uk
Web site: <http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/bodcmain.html>

Environmental Information Centre

CEH Institute of Terrestrial Ecology
Monks Wood
Abbots Ripton
Huntingdon
Cams
PE17 2LS

Tel: +44 (0) 1487 773381
Fax: +44 (0) 1487 773467
e-mail: eic@ite.ac.uk
Web page: <http://www.nmw.ac.uk/ite/eic1.html>

National Geosciences Information Service

British Geological Survey
Keyworth
Nottingham
NG12 5GG

Tel: +44 (0) 115 936 3109
Fax: +44 (0) 115 936 3276
e-mail: ngis@bgs.ac.uk
Web site: <http://www.bgs.ac.uk/bgs/w3/iserg/ngiswww.html>

The National Water Archive

CEH Institute of Hydrology
Wallingford
Oxfordshire
OX10 8BB

Tel: +44 (0) 1491 838800
Fax: +44 (0) 1491 692424
e-mail: nwamail@ioh.ac.uk
Web site: <http://www.nwl.ac.uk/~nrfadata/nwa.html>

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton
Didcot
Oxfordshire
OX11 0QX

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Fax: +44 (0) 1235 445848
e-mail: neodc@rl.ac.uk
Web site: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/>

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